

ISic3092

I.Sicily inscription 3092

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331418

1. [— — —]ΤΩΝ [— — — — —]
2. [— — —]ΗΘΗΗ [— τῆς μηνός]
3. [Ἰουλί]ου δέ [κα ἐν τῆ]
4. [ὑπατί]α Βα [λεντ. καὶ Βαλεντ. —']
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645440

PHI 331418

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0863

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*.
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